

STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *In the process of transforming the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the creation of textile and sewing-knitting complexes, the production of finished products with high added value, the expansion of volumes and types of products that are in high demand in the domestic and foreign markets, as well as providing employment for the population are being carried out. An analysis of the work carried out in the field will help develop measures to eliminate shortcomings in the field.*

Keywords: *light industry, textile industry, export, textile production, personnel management, employees.*

The economic and social significance of more efficient development of the industry, in general, of the textile industry, which is considered its main link, the high demand for finished products produced by the industry and the employment of a significant part of the population determine the Increase in the depth of processing of raw materials and its development generate the need to increase the types of finished products and improve the technological cycle production of finished products.

Light industry of Uzbekistan is one of the leading and rapidly developing industries. In particular, textile enterprises, which are the main component of light industry, play an important role in solving the economic and at the same time social problems of the country. This industry also provides employment to the population, especially the economically active layer of women in society, and improves living conditions.

The textile industry occupies one of the most important places in the republic's economy, it is one of the main industries that produce consumer goods (sewing products, fabric and gauze and knitted products), which are the most important element of the market.

An analysis of trends in socio-economic development shows that the share of light industry in the economy of Uzbekistan, especially the textile industry, which occupies a significant place in its development, is rapidly growing in terms of economic growth in countries around the world. This industry plays a central role in the production of industrial products, since this industry, along with the production of consumer goods, provides employment to the country's population, which, in turn, is an important factor in the socio-economic development of the republic. In addition, the network ensures the republic's activity in foreign economic relations, including the number of enterprises created on the basis of foreign investments in this network, which increases every day.

In January 2022, there were 18 004 enterprises with the main activities of textile manufacturing, clothing manufacturing, and leather goods and related products manufacturing. As of January 1, 2023, the “O‘zto‘qimachilik sanoat” association includes 1 989 state-registered textile enterprises.

The main branch of the textile industry, i.e., 75% comes from cotton fiber processing enterprises. Wool fiber processing plants account for 15% of the textile industry, and the remaining

parts are equally divided between 3% of flax stem and hemp fiber processing plants, 5% of silk fiber processing plants and 2% of pure man-made fiber processing plants.

Figure 1. The number of textile enterprises in Uzbekistan (2017-2022)

In recent years, the share of textile production enterprises among industrial enterprises in our republic has been increasing. The following table shows the growth rate of the country's GDP and the growth rate of textile products in its composition (Table 1).

The share of the textile industry in the gross domestic product of the republic in 2022 will exceed 9%, more than 150 enterprises process more than 1 million tons of cotton fiber. A clear confirmation of this is the export of textiles and clothing and knitwear products in the amount of 3 billion 229.2 million US dollars in 2022, the growth rate of which increased by 10.2% compared to the previous year. The share of finished products in exports amounted to 41.5 percent. This represents an increase of 44 percent compared to 2021. An important factor in achieving such a positive result was the increase in the number of exporting enterprises from 96 to 1503.

The share of the textile industry in the total industrial output of our country increased from 5.2 percent in 2016 to 7.3 percent in 2022, which indicates its rapid development compared to other sectors of the economy.

According to the above information, in 2022 the gross domestic product (GDP) of the Republic of Uzbekistan at current prices will be \$888,314.7 billion. in soums, increased by 5.7% compared to 2021. In 2022, the volume of industrial production will be 553 billion 265.0 billion. compared to 2021, this figure increased by 121.3%.

Textile production and the clothing production network also have their place in the industry, and in 2022 the volume of textile products in the industrial production of our country will amount to 460,491.8 billion pieces. soums (8.2 times more than in 2012 or 20% more than in 2021) and 17264.8 billion soums were created. Sewing products worth soums were produced (17.3 times more than in 2012, or 27% more than in 2021).

The key to success in ensuring the rapid and safe development of the competitiveness of products of industrial enterprises is comprehensive and justified measures, main tasks and directions, development and clear definition of concepts of economic development at various levels for the coming period.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our republic, comprehensive positive results have been achieved in the production of industrial products and ensuring their competitiveness.

Table 1.

Growth rates of GDP and textile sector of the economy of Uzbekistan (in billions of soums)[1]

Indicators	Years										
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
GDP billion soums	120,1	144,5	177,2	210,2	242,5	317,5	426,6	532,7	605,5	738,4	605,5
Volume of industrial products	57,6	70,6	84,2	97,6	111,9	148,8	235,3	322,5	368,7	456,0	553,2
The volume of industrial production	43,6	55,3	67,1	77,1	89,8	117,7	189,6	254,8	305,9	378,1	460,5
Production volume of textile products	7,6	8,9	10,8	13,2	13,3	16,8	24,8	29,9	36,7	52,3	62,8
The volume of clothing production products	0,9	1,1	1,3	1,5	4,3	6,1	7,7	9,1	10,4	13,6	17,2

These development indicators indicate that the government of our republic is paying serious attention to the further development of the textile industry. As a result, the production capacity of value-added textile products has increased, especially since this industry employs 13.7% of Uzbekistan's 1,810,600 people working in the industry. In particular, 132,478 (53.6%) women employed in the economy work in textile production enterprises.

Table 2.

Dynamics of employed employees and created jobs in textile enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2022[1]

Indicator	2017 y.	2018 y.	2019 y.	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.
Total number of employees, (person)	173 631	188 176	215 869	217 913	235 121	247 245
<i>including:</i>						
women, (man)	83 784	96 428	114 890	118 897	128 136	132 478
men, (man)	89 847	91 748	100 979	99 016	106 985	114 767
Number of jobs, (place)	185 262	205 626	233 144	228 947	251 782	264 120
Number of available vacancies, (position)	9 792	11 557	9 907	11 143	10 178	10 394

The population of Uzbekistan at the beginning of 2018 was 32,656.7 thousand people, of which 49.8% were women, and at the beginning of 2023 this figure will be 36,024.9 thousand people, of which 17,896.3 thousand people those. 49.7% are women. Based on Table 1, we can conclude that the number of employees in the textile industry is growing year by year, which, in turn, significantly contributes to reducing the unemployment rate in the country. In 2017, women made up 48.2% of the workforce, and by 2022 this figure will increase to 53.6%. In 2017, the

number of men working in the industry exceeded the number of women by 6,063,000, and in 2022 this trend showed the opposite growth, i.e., the number of women exceeded the number of men by 17,711,000. As a result of the increase in the number of enterprises created in this industry, we clearly see that the number of jobs created in the industry in 2022 increased by 1.43 times compared to 2017. The dynamics of the number of available vacancies in the industry fluctuates, which, in turn, is due to the fact that a significant part of the workers in the industry are women and they are employed in seasonal work.

Various measures are being implemented and continue to be taken aimed at modernizing and diversifying the country's textile industry, ensuring its dynamic development, increasing the range and volume of production of competitive products, and increasing demand for them in foreign markets. In the process of these transformations, it will be possible to reduce the necessary costs for organizing research and development work, and improving the qualifications of personnel involved in the production process. As a result of intersectoral cooperation, the conditions for attracting investments, the process of distributing investments across areas of activity will be improved, and high-quality human capital will be formed.

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